

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/scan
hash://md5/c01a446f655da7014e77cc53d5a359bf

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scan/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/scan, has fingerprint hash://md5/c01a446f655da7014e77cc53d5a359bf, is 351MiB in size and contains 355,796 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 20,579 primary taxa (e.g., Arthropoda) and 39,667 associated taxa (e.g., ex. rotten banana-brown sugar BAIT). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

ABS-ARTHARCH DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Archbold Biological Station Arthropod Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/ABS-ARTHARCH_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z BLM-MLFO DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for BLM Mother Lode Field Office: The Bees of Pine Hill Preserve https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/BLM-MLFO_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z BURKLE-LAMANNA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Plant-pollinator community assembly across wildfire gradients https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/BURKLE-LAMANNA_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z CC-OBE-COCOA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Colorado College Arthropod Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/CC-OBE-COCOA_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z CLEV-CMNHENT DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Cleveland Museum of Natural History Invertebrate Zoology Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/CLEV-CMNHENT_DwC-

A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z DEBU-ENT DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Guelph Insect Collection (DEBU) https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/DEBU-ENT_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z EGC-EGC_CRC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Eric G Chapman Coleoptera Research Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/EGC-EGC_CRC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z GPSC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Gregory P. Setliff Collection - Kutztown University https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/GPSC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z GUAM-ESUG DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Guam Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/GUAM-ESUG_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z HDOA-HDOAPPC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Hawaii Department of Agriculture, Plant Pest Control Branch https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/HDOA-HDOAPPC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z KY-UKIC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Kentucky Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/KY-UKIC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z LEPSOC-LEPSOC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for The Lepidopterists' Society Season Summary https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/LEPSOC-LEPSOC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MC-MCIC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Middlebury College Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MC-MCIC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MELU-AFI DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Australian Freshwater Invertebrates https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MELU-AFI_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MISSA-MEM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Mississippi Entomological Museum https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MISSA-MEM_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MSB-PARA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Museum of Southwestern Biology Division of Parasitology - ParasiteTracker https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MSB-PARA_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MTU-MTUIC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Michigan Technological University Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MTU-MTUIC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z MV-MVBC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Michael Veit Bee Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/MV-MVBC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z NAUF-NAUF5F DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for NAU Forest Entomology Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/NAUF-NAUF5F_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z NCSUR-NCSU_ACEYDSC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for NCSU

Research Dataset Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/NCSUR-NCSU_ACEYDSC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z NYSM-ARTH DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for New York State Museum Arthropod Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/NYSM-ARTH_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z PALA-RES DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Lasioglossum (Dialictus) new species in Yucatan https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/PALA-RES_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z PSU-LUL DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for López-Uribe Lab Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/PSU-LUL_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z PU-PERC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for The Purdue Entomological Research Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/PU-PERC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z RLMC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for RL Minckley Insect and Plant Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/RLMC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z RMBL-ENT DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Rocky Mountain Biological Laboratory Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/RMBL-ENT_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z RUBC-RUAC_ENT DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Rutgers University Entomological Museum https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/RUBC-RUAC_ENT_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z TAMU-TAMUIC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Texas A&M University Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/TAMU-TAMUIC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UCM-UCMC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Colorado Museum of Natural History Entomology Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UCM-UCMC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UD-UDCC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Delaware Insect Research Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UD-UDCC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UFIFAS-UFFE DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Florida Forestry Entomology Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UFIFAS-UFFE_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UI-WFBM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for William F. Barr Entomological Museum https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UI-WFBM_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UKY-HIC-HIC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Hymenoptera Institute Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UKY-HIC-HIC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UMD-UMDI DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Minnesota Duluth Insect Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UMD-UMDI_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UNI-UNIAW DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Northern Iowa - Wen

Research Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UNI-UNIAW_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UNL-NSM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Harold W. Manter Laboratory of Parasitology Collection (HWML) Parasite Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UNL-NSM_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UNM-MSBA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Museum of Southwestern Biology, Division of Arthropods https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UNM-MSBA_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UNSM-UNSM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Nebraska State Museum https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UNSM-UNSM_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UT-UTBFL DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Pardee et al. 2023: Plant-Pollinator Networks across an Urban Corridor https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UT-UTBFL_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z UWM-WIRC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Wisconsin Insect Research Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/UWM-WIRC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z WICH-WICHI DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Wichita State University Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/WICH-WICHI_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z WSU-WSUC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Washington State University Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/WSU-WSUC_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z WVW-ENT DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for West Virginia Wesleyan College Katharine B. Gregg Orchid Pollinator Collection https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/content/dwca/WVW-ENT_DwC-A.zip 2026-01-24T05:55:38.319Z hash://md5/c01a446f655da7014e77cc53d5a359bf

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scan> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1

tool name	version
elton	0.16.4
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 351MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/scan

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/scan\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/scan\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/scan\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/scan`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/scan`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/scan`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/scan`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/scan`, has fingerprint hash://md5/c01a446f655da7014e77cc53d5a359bf, is 351MiB in size and contains 355,796 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 20,579 primary taxa (e.g., `Arthropoda`) and 39,667 associated taxa (e.g., `ex. rotten banana-brown sugar BAIT`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Aphaenogaster treatae	interactsWith	Quercus inopina	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Aphaenogaster umphreyi	interactsWith	Quercus inopina	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Aphaenogaster flemingi	interactsWith	Bufo terrestris	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Aphaenogaster lamellidens	interactsWith	Sabal palmetto	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	151146
hasHost	124612
adjacentTo	46729
parasiteOf	31421
coOccursWith	996
eats	743
visits	120
killedBy	14
hasParasite	14
ectoparasiteOf	1

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Arthropoda	6039
Cestoda	5511
Lasioglossum	5449
Andrena	4089
Nematoda	3811
Acari	3769
Taenia	3684
Toxascaris	3404
Echinococcus multilocularis	3064
Aphelinus albipodus	2263
Aphytis hispanicus	2143
Cediopsylla simplex	2114
Acanthoscelides aureolus	1855
Echinococcus	1685
Aphytis comperei	1682
Lasioglossum (Dialictus)	1637
Bombus	1597
Halictus ligatus	1593
Mastophorus dipodomis	1572

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
ex. rotten banana-brown sugar BAIT	7780
not recorded	6938
Alopex	3968
Dipodomys merriami	2714
Larrea tridentata	2324
Mearns Cottontail	2313
Ulmus crassifolia	2236
Quercus virginiana	2164
Quercus buckleyi	2153
Procyon lotor	1842
ex. chaff scale	1731
Prosopis velutina	1710
Peromyscus leucopus	1708
Salix	1622
grapefruit	1555
Juniperus ashei	1539
Solidago	1507
Microtus pennsylvanicus	1475
Sphaeralcea laxa	1371

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Cediopsylla simplex	adjacentTo	Mearns Cottontail	1472
Taenia	hasHost	Alopex	1206
Toxascaris	hasHost	Alopex	1178
Aphytis hispanicus	hasHost	ex. chaff scale	857
Algarobius prosopis	interactsWith	seeds Prosopis juliflora	803
Aphytis hispanicus	adjacentTo	grapefruit	784
Aphelinus albipodus	hasHost	Diuraphis noxia	780
Aphelinus albipodus	adjacentTo	wheat	777

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Bactrocera ochrosiae	interactsWith	Ochrosia mariannensis	776
Aphytis comperei	hasHost	ex. chaff scale	734
Echinococcus multilocularis	hasHost	Alopex	721
Haemaphysalis leporispalustris	adjacentTo	Mearns Cottontail	628
Araecerus fasciculatus	interactsWith	Leucaena leucocephala	613
Unknown sp.3	interactsWith	Neisosperma oppositifolia	610
Unidentified spp_unidentified	interactsWith	not recorded	556
Lasioglossum (Dialictus)	interactsWith	Neptunia lutea	498
Oropsylla bruneri	interactsWith	Ictidomys tridecemlineatus	492
Aphytis comperei	adjacentTo	grapefruit	492
Erythroneura	adjacentTo	Ulmus crassifolia	487

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Plantain	NONE	col	Plantain
Pollinia	SYNONYM_OF	col	Chrysopogon
Pollinia	SYNONYM_OF	col	Eulalia
Pollinia	SYNONYM_OF	col	Charpentieria

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	14398
col	class	13
col	family	327
col	form	1
col	genus	3251
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	3
col	infraspecific name	3
col	kingdom	4
col	nanorder	1
col	order	32
col	parvorder	1
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	8
col	section	1
col	species	17359
col	subclass	3
col	subfamily	34
col	subgenus	105
col	suborder	6
col	subspecies	401
col	subterclass	1
col	subtribe	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	superfamily	18
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	5
col	unranked	2
col	variety	82
discoverlife	NA	34429
discoverlife	species	1377
gbif	NA	10992
gbif	class	14
gbif	family	355
gbif	form	4
gbif	genus	3725
gbif	kingdom	6
gbif	order	28
gbif	phylum	8
gbif	species	20240
gbif	subspecies	518
gbif	variety	131
itis	NA	18195
itis	class	11
itis	family	323
itis	genus	2652
itis	infraorder	2
itis	infraphylum	1
itis	kingdom	4
itis	order	40
itis	phylum	10
itis	species	14163
itis	subclass	8
itis	subfamily	42
itis	subgenus	4
itis	suborder	8
itis	subphylum	1
itis	subspecies	261
itis	superclass	1
itis	superfamily	6
itis	superorder	3
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	87
mdd	NA	35805
ncbi	NA	19142
ncbi	clade	2
ncbi	class	12
ncbi	cohort	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	family	333
ncbi	genus	3220
ncbi	infraorder	5
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	32
ncbi	phylum	8
ncbi	section	1
ncbi	species	12825
ncbi	subclass	8
ncbi	subfamily	51
ncbi	subgenus	56
ncbi	suborder	7
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	subspecies	114
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	17
ncbi	superkingdom	1
ncbi	superorder	4
ncbi	tribe	4
ncbi	varietas	11
pdb	NA	32478
pdb	class	15
pdb	family	244
pdb	genus	1283
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	3
pdb	kingdom	4
pdb	order	28
pdb	phylum	6
pdb	species	1668
pdb	subclass	1
pdb	subfamily	48
pdb	subgenus	1
pdb	subkingdom	1
pdb	suborder	9
pdb	subspecies	1
pdb	subtribe	3
pdb	superclass	1
pdb	superfamily	8
pdb	superorder	2
pdb	superphylum	1
pdb	tribe	9
pdb	unranked clade	17

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
tpt	NA	33395
tpt	family	30
tpt	genus	256
tpt	order	4
tpt	species	2120
tpt	specificepithet	1
tpt	subspecificepithet	5
wfo	NA	32506
wfo	family	33
wfo	genus	709
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	2478
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	60
wfo	tribe	1
wfo	variety	57
worms	NA	28129
worms	class	11
worms	family	251
worms	forma	1
worms	genus	1738
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraorder	4
worms	infraphylum	1
worms	kingdom	5
worms	order	34
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	7
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	5553
worms	subclass	8
worms	subfamily	6
worms	subgenus	4
worms	suborder	8
worms	subphylum	2
worms	subspecies	19
worms	subterclass	1
worms	superfamily	16
worms	superorder	1
worms	tribe	2
worms	variety	17

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	37880
col	SYNONYM_OF	6521
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	27095
discoverlife	NONE	64676
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	754
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2575
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	129
gbif	NONE	33864
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	10095
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	33029
itis	NONE	41923
itis	SYNONYM_OF	2546
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	23383
mdd	NONE	66326
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	869
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	41
ncbi	NONE	43166
ncbi	SAME_AS	22863
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	1732
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	59
pbdb	NONE	61333
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5625
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	573
tpt	NONE	63935
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3371
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	737
wfo	NONE	60979
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	1501
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5493
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	552
worms	NONE	56719
worms	SYNONYM_OF	2177
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	9156

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-29T05:28:56Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scan/archi
2026-01-29T05:28:56Z	summary	355796 interaction(s)
2026-01-29T05:28:56Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-01-29T05:28:56Z	summary	140 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-29) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

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